

Abstract

Research in Chikung (Qigong) – A Partnership Between IPTC and ICBAS.

Jorge Magalhães Rodrigues^{1,2*} .

¹ IPTC - Research Department in Complementary Therapies, Portuguese Institute of *Taiji* and *Qigong*, Porto, Portugal;

² ICBAS-UP - School of Medicine and Biomedical Sciences, University of Porto, Portugal.

* Correspondence: dep.investig-IPTC@outlook.pt

Abstract

Human development and well-being are fundamentally dependent on a balance between physical activity, proper nutrition, and mental health. Within the context of Traditional Chinese Medicine, Chikung (*Qigong*) and Taichi (*Taijiquan*) emerge as Traditional Applied Psychophysiological Feedback Therapies that integrate physical, respiratory, and mental exercises to impact physiological regulation. This work presents the research line resulting from the partnership between IPTC and ICBAS-UP, focused on evaluating the efficacy of these practices across various clinical and social contexts. The developed research spans diverse populations and pathologies, with key highlights including:

- Paediatrics and Adolescence: Pilot studies demonstrated significant improvements in children with behavioural disorders, such as Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) and Oppositional Defiant Disorder (ODD), evaluated through Achenbach’s Teacher’s Report Form (TRF) scores. Additionally, the potential of *Taijiquan* and *Qigong* was observed in treating co-thymia (mixed anxiety-depressive disorder) in school-age children.
- School Context and Academic Stress: Randomized controlled trials (RCT) among high-school students revealed a significant decrease in anxiety levels, measured via the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI) and salivary cortisol tests, in the *Qigong* group compared to control groups. Systematic reviews also corroborate the efficacy of *Qigong* in treating children with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) and promoting general well-being through traditional systems such as *Wu Qin Xi* (Five Animal *Qigong*).
- Occupational Health: During the COVID-19 pandemic, research extended to combating burnout and emotional exhaustion among nurses and teachers. Results indicated that 70% of participants in the intervention groups showed significantly decreased levels of exhaustion following *Qigong* practice.

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In conclusion, the IPTC/ICBAS collaboration has been essential in validating *Qigong* as an effective complementary tool. This partnership has successfully adapted to the digital transformation by implementing online programs to ensure accessibility and continuity of mental health care.

Keywords: *Qigong; Taijiquan; Mental Health; Clinical Research; Complementary Therapies.*

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